

Visigothic Homoian Christianity

also known as “Arianism in the Visigothic Kingdom”, “Visigothic Christianity”, “Homoeanism amongst Visigoths”, “Homoianism amongst Visigoths”, “Homoian Christianity amongst Visigoths”

By Cédrik Michel, Durham University

Entry tags: Arianism, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Christianity

Homoian (also homoean) Christians, from the ancient Greek homoios (ὅμοιος), meaning similar, believed that God the Father, and Christ the Son were similar in nature. This was distinct from Nicene Christianity which adhered to the view that the Father and Son were identical (homos-ὁμός) in nature. The theological position of Homoianism was presented at the Councils of Ariminum and Seleucia in 359 and ratified at the Council of Constantinople in 360 CE. Homoianism was favored by the emperors Constantius II and Valens. Homoian Christianity was championed by Acacius of Caesarea (died in 365 CE) and its followers were sometimes called 'Acacians'. Arianism is often used (erroneously) in scholarship as a synonym for Homoian Christianity (as well as other theological positions rejecting the notion that the Son and Father are of the same nature). This stems from attempts by fifth-century CE opponents to slander Homoianism through association with the Alexandrian priest Arius (c.250 or 256-336 CE), who also believed that the nature of the Son was distinct from that of the Father. Like other instances of religious conversion in Antiquity, the adoption of Homoian Christianity amongst Goths was a gradual process rather than a punctual event. The genesis of Homoian gothic communities occurred in 341 when Ulfilas (also Wulfila, c.311-383 CE), considered the apostle of the Goths, was appointed bishop of the Homoian (or a theological position best described as Homoian) communities in Gothic-controlled lands at the Council of Antioch. This would imply that there were indeed Christians already living in this area who had requested for a bishop. These may have been the descendants of Christian, Roman prisoners. He preached to and converted Gothic communities north of the Danube until he was expelled, along with many of his followers in 347/8 due to a Christian persecution in Gothia. Ulfilas and his followers settled in Moesia, in the Roman Empire. He developed a Gothic script and translated the Bible into Gothic. Homoian Christianity received imperial patronage from the emperors Constantius II from 350-61, during his time as sole ruler of the Empire, and from Valens until his death in 378. During this time, Ulfila's Gothic followers would adopt Homoianism, understood as a compromise between so-called 'Arianism' and Nicene Christianity due to its stipulation that the nature of Christ was similar to that of the Father. During the reign of these two emperors, two other events can be pinpointed as part of the conversion process of Goths. In 369, a power struggle occurred within the Thervingian people between Athanaric and Fritigern. Fritigern petitioned for support from the Roman emperor Valens. The Thervingian Goths under Fritigern's command converted to Homoian Christianity and requested theological teachers. In 376, the westward movement of the Huns and Alans encroached on Gothic land and two gothic Groups, the Thervingi and Greuthungi, requested to cross the Danube into Roman land to seek refuge. The Thervingi were allowed to cross but the Greuthungi were denied entry. Nevertheless, the Greuthungi crossed into Roman land illegally. Conversion to Homoianism was a condition for admission and would have applied to all Goths entering the Empire at this time. The Council of Constantinople of 381, summoned by emperor Theodosius I, condemned Arianism (and its associate theological doctrine, Homoianism). Nevertheless, Homoianism was allowed to flourish amongst barbarian peoples, who were allowed to worship in the ways that already existed at the time of their ancestors. Scholars such as Herwig Wolfram argue that the conversion of Goths to Homoianism would have created a sense of unity, a distinct change from the heterogenous pagan beliefs from the pre-Christian era. The exact ethnogenesis of the Visigoths, as a sub-group of Goths and other barbarian peoples has been disputed, but it seems likely that the identity of this group solidified under the Alaric in the 390s, until their definitive settlement in Aquitaine in 419 by the Roman Empire. Homoian Christianity became deeply entrenched within the ranks

of the Visigothic aristocracy. Many Homoian bishops originated from aristocratic families. In 579, Hermenegild, the son of king Liuvigild, converted to Nicene Christianity and led a revolt in Baetica. Liuvigild called a synod in Toledo in 580 which revised Homoian beliefs to be more acceptable to Nicene Christians. These reforms would have little impact given that Homoianism had already largely lost its appeal since the 560s, if not earlier. In the second half of the sixth century, Nicene and Homoian clergy, bishops and churches would be operating in parallel in most major cities in the Visigothic Kingdom. Homoian Christianity would be replaced by Nicene Christianity as the state-sponsored religion at the third council of Toledo, in 589, convoked by king Reccared, who had himself converted to Nicene Christianity in 587. Former Homoian bishops were allowed to keep their posts and shared their duties with their Nicene counterparts, but metropolitans lost their province-wide authority.

Date Range: 341 CE - 589 CE

Region: Visigothic Kingdom

Region tags: Europe, Western Europe

This is an approximate replica of the map of the Visigothic Kingdom contained in Roger Collins' 'Visigothic Kingdom 409-711'.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Berndt, Guido M., and Roland Steinacher, eds. *Arianism: Roman Heresy and Barbarian Creed*. Farnham, Surrey; Burlington: Ashgate, 2014.
- Source 2: Heather, P. J., and John Matthews. *The Goths in the Fourth Century*. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 1991.
- Source 3: Heather, Peter. 'The Crossing of the Danube and the Gothic Conversion'. *Greek, Roman and Byzantine Studies* 27, no. 3 (1986): 289–318.

Reference: Geary, Patrick J.. "Barbarians and Ethnicity". In *Late Antiquity: A Guide to the Postclassical World*, 107–29. Cambridge, MA; London: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 1999.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.themiddleages.net/visigoths.html>
- Source 1 Description: Overview of the history of the Visigoths
- Source 1 URL: <https://ccel.org/ccel/schaff/hcc4/hcc4.ii.xvi.html>
- Source 1 Description: History of the Christian Church by Philip Schaff: Arian Christianity among the Goths and other German Tribes.

Notes: Unfortunately few resources about Gothic Homoian communities are available online. Most lack precision or are approached from a modern theological perspective.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/fathers/2601.htm>

– Source 1 Description: Socrates Scholasticus' History of the Church

– Source 2 URL: https://penelope.uchicago.edu/Thayer/E/Roman/Texts/Ammian/31*.html

– Source 2 Description: Ammianus Marcellinus' Res Gestae book 31

– Source 3 URL: <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/basis/gregory-hist.asp>

– Source 3 Description: Gregory of Tours, History of the Franks

Notes: Throughout his historical work, Gregory combats Arianism-used as a derogatory term to describe Homoian beliefs-even though it had, for the most part, been eliminated in Gaul and Spain.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Follows the Old and New Testaments of the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus was made of flesh, but of a similar nature as God the Father.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Visigoths had Nicene subjects in Hispania. Much of the Homoian presence in the Visigothic kingdom was contained within the aristocracy.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Homoianism abhorred Nicene Christian intervention. Judaism was tolerated however.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There was violent suppression of Priscillianism in Hispania in the fifth and sixth centuries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population,

numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although Homoians in the Visigothic Kingdom were tolerant of other religious groups, for example Jews.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religion have official political support

— Yes

Notes: Homoianism was especially prevalent in the aristocracy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

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Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

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Specific to this answer:

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Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

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Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

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Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

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Notes: Yes, although Homoians in the Visigothic Kingdom were tolerant of other religious groups, for

example Jews.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– I don't know

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Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Follows the Old and New Testaments of the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus was made of flesh, but of a similar nature as God the Father.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious

community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Adultery:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Anal and Oral sex

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

–Yes [specify]: God protects and favors the pious.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are supernatural beings present:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

— Yes

Notes: God the Father is the only and supreme God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

— Yes [specify]: Sources assign divine authority and approval to Visigothic kings

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: There are no distinctions with Nicene Christianity in this regard, to my knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Although with the Holy Trinity and the cult of martyrs, worship could be directed towards other beings without denying the supreme nature of God the Father.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: No difference from Nicene Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Notes: Jesus and the cult of martyrs could perhaps qualify as previously human spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: God the Father and the Holy Spirit

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Indeed, the nature of Christ and God the father was similar, but distinct.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: God the Father, through the Holy Spirit, and the Virgin Mary begot Christ. Jesus is considered the Son of God.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: God the Father is supreme over all.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: No differences in burial from other forms of Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Although 'Homoian' and pagan Gothic grave goods are not distinct.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: No differences in burial from other forms of Christianity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Although 'Homoian' and pagan Gothic grave goods are not distinct.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: God the Father is the only and supreme God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Sources assign divine authority and approval to Visigothic kings

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: There are no distinctions with Nicene Christianity in this regard, to my knowledge.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Although with the Holy Trinity and the cult of martyrs, worship could be directed towards other beings without denying the supreme nature of God the Father.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: No difference from Nicene Christianity.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Notes: Jesus and the cult of martyrs could perhaps qualify as previously human spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: God the Father and the Holy Spirit

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Indeed, the nature of Christ and God the father was similar, but distinct.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: God the Father, through the Holy Spirit, and the Virgin Mary begot Christ. Jesus is considered the Son of God.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: God the Father is supreme over all.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Anal and Oral sex

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: God protects and favors the pious.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Like in Christianity more generally, it is strongly recommended, but not required.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Recommended at certain times, but not required

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Christianity more generally advocates for charity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Although Christians were expected to follow the 10 Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: The communal aspect of early Christianity is stressed in our sources. 'Good' Christians were expected to go to church.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of

governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

— No

Notes: Although a small amount of wine is given at Communion to symbolize the blood of Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Like in Christianity more generally, it is strongly recommended, but not required.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Recommended at certain times, but not required

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Christianity more generally advocates for charity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at

meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Although Christians were expected to follow the 10 Commandments.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: The communal aspect of early Christianity is stressed in our sources. 'Good' Christians were expected to go to church.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No

Notes: Although a small amount of wine is given at Communion to symbolize the blood of Christ.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE
Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Visigothic Kingdom

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Although individuals wanting to join the ranks of the clergy would be given a suitable theological education.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a hierarchy in the Visigothic Homoian church which adheres to the power structure of Nicene Christianity, i.e. archbishops, bishops, priest.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Arianism is not seen as a proselytizing or persecuting faith. Gothic contingents in the Roman army would ask for churches in which they could worship without interference from Nicene Christians.

Reference: Geary, Patrick J.. "Barbarians and Ethnicity". In *Late Antiquity: A Guide to the Postclassical World*, 107-29. Cambridge, MA; London: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 1999.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Ulfilas translated the Bible in Gothic. The extent to which Gothic was spoken outside the Church is unclear. Gothic was also spoken in the Ostrogothic Kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Visigothic Homoian calendar may have had added days celebrating the death of Gothic martyrs. See Heather and Matthews p.121-22 for a translation of a Gothic Homoian calendar from Italy.

Reference: Heather, Peter J., and John Matthews. *The Goths in the Fourth Century*. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 1991.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, the army of the Visigothic Kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Taxes would be paid to the Visigothic Kingdom.

Reference: Castellanos, Santiago. "The Political Nature of Taxation in Visigothic Spain". *Early Medieval Europe* 12 (2004): 201-28.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Latin was also spoken. Goths stationed in the East would also have learned some Greek.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

— Yes

Notes: Homoian bishops and other clerical personnel would also interact with the Visigothic aristocracy and the king. Religion and politics were deeply intertwined in Antiquity and the Middle Ages.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Visigothic army.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Religious councils could be called to debate theological issues. For instance, numerous councils were called to eradicate Priscillianism.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latin was the language of law codes and government.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management would have been provided by the Visigothic Kingdom using the tax revenue.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They would adhere to the laws of the Visigothic Kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: They would adhere to the punishments stipulated in Visigothic law.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The Visigothic Kingdom would provide for the infrastructure using tax revenues.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Visigothic law.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Visigothic Kingdom

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Although individuals wanting to join the ranks of the clergy would be given a suitable theological education.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a hierarchy in the Visigothic Homoian church which adheres to the power structure of Nicene Christianity, i.e. archbishops, bishops, priest.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Homoian bishops and other clerical personnel would also interact with the Visigothic aristocracy and the king. Religion and politics were deeply intertwined in Antiquity and the Middle Ages.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management would have been provided by the Visigothic Kingdom using the tax revenue.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Visigothic Kingdom would provide for the infrastructure using tax revenues.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes would be paid to the Visigothic Kingdom.

Reference: Castellanos, Santiago. "The Political Nature of Taxation in Visigothic Spain". *Early Medieval Europe* 12 (2004): 201-28.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Religious councils could be called to debate theological issues. For instance, numerous councils were called to eradicate Priscillianism.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They would adhere to the laws of the Visigothic Kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They would adhere to the punishments stipulated in Visigothic law.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Visigothic law.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Arianism is not seen as a proselytizing or persecuting faith. Gothic contingents in the Roman army would ask for churches in which they could worship without interference from Nicene Christians.

Reference: Geary, Patrick J.. "Barbarians and Ethnicity". In *Late Antiquity: A Guide to the Postclassical World*, 107-29. Cambridge, MA; London: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 1999.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the army of the Visigothic Kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Visigothic army.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Ulfilas translated the Bible in Gothic. The extent to which Gothic was spoken outside the Church is unclear. Gothic was also spoken in the Ostrogothic Kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latin was also spoken. Goths stationed in the East would also have learned some Greek.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Latin was the language of law codes and government.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Visigothic Homoian calendar may have had added days celebrating the death of Gothic martyrs. See Heather and Matthews p.121-22 for a translation of a Gothic Homoian calendar from Italy.

Reference: Heather, Peter J., and John Matthews. *The Goths in the Fourth Century*. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 1991.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

Food Production

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 341 CE - 399 CE

Region: Roman Empire (Greatest Extent)

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